

Managing Editor's Column

Vol. 30, No. 10

Dear Readers,

Following the publication of the J.UCS special issue ‘Fighting Cybersecurity Risks from a Multidisciplinary Perspective’ by our esteemed guest editors Steffen Wendzel, Aleksandra Mileva, Virginia N. L. Franqueira and Martin Gilje in mid-September, I am very pleased to announce today the ninth J.UCS regular issue of 2024. In this issue, various topical aspects of computer science are covered by 26 authors from 8 countries (Algeria, Brazil, India, Indonesia, Ireland, Israel, Serbia, Sri Lanka) in 6 articles. As always, I would like to thank all the authors for their sound research and the editorial board for their highly valuable review effort and suggestions for improvement. These contributions, together with the generous support of the consortium members, sustain the quality of our journal.

As we want to secure the financial support also for the years to come, we are looking for institutions and libraries to financially support our diamond open access journal as part of the KOALA initiative. Please think about the possibility of such financial participation by your institution in the computer science and mathematics cluster of the KOALA initiative together with a lot of other active members, we would be very grateful for any kind of support.

In an ongoing effort to further strengthen our journal, I would like to expand the editorial board: If you are a tenured associate professor or above with a strong publication record, you are welcome to apply to join our editorial board. We are also interested in receiving high-quality proposals for special issues on new topics and trends. Please consider yourself and encourage your colleagues to submit high-quality articles or special issue proposals for our journal.

In this regular issue, I am very pleased to introduce the following 6 accepted articles: Panji Bintoro, Zulkifli Zulkifli, Yaya Heryadi, Fitriana Fitriana, Nopi Anggista Putri, and Dwi Yana Ayu Andini introduce their research on the automatic detection of systemic diseases to recognize Mpox virus using GPLNet based on skin lesions. In their research, Farhad Lotfi, Branka Rodić, Aleksandra Labus, and Zorica Bogdanović from Serbia are looking at predicting university students' anxiety by using supervised learning algorithms with providing pertinent feedback. Michele dos Santos Soares, Cássio Andrade Furukawa, Maria Istela Cagnin, and Débora Maria Barroso Paiva from Brazil discuss their research findings on identifying the accessibility barriers faced by the community of blind students and highlighting the main factors that hinder this community from accessing learning objects. Houda Tadjer, Zohra Mehenaoui, Yacine Lafif, Amira Chemmakh, and Asanka P. Sayakkara from Algeria discuss their research on time management for effective learning based on students' temporal traces and the production of automatic feedback in an online learning environment. In a collaborative

research effort between Sri Lanka, Ireland and Israel, Lojena Navanesan, Nhien-An Le-Khac, Yossi Oren, and Asanka P. Sayakkara cover in their research cross-device portability of machine learning models in electromagnetic side-channel analysis for forensics. Last but not least, Ujjwala Thakur, Ankit Vidyarthi, and Amarjeet Prajapati from India cover the latest research on video activity recognition by introducing a robust framework that leverages the power of a stacked Bidirectional Long Short-Term Memory (Bi-LSTM) and Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU) architecture, harmonized within a fusion-based deep model.

Enjoy Reading!

Best regards,

Christian Gütl, Managing Editor
Graz University of Technology, Graz, Austria
Email: c.guetl@tugraz.at